

Digital Solutions to Support Transition from Linear to Circular Manufacturing

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Abstract

The transition from linear to circular manufacturing systems (CMS) is essential for manufacturing firms aiming to enhance sustainability and mitigate resource depletion. Despite clear environmental and economic benefits, the adoption of circular economy (CE) principles within the manufacturing sector remains limited, largely due to significant technological, operational, and organisational barriers. This study addresses these issues by exploring the specific challenges that manufacturing companies face during their transition to CMS and proposes digital technologies to effectively overcome these barriers. Utilising an exploratory, qualitative, single-case study approach, we investigated a European white goods manufacturer implementing a refurbishment centre aimed at establishing circular practices within their laundry appliance segment. Through thematic analysis, we identified three primary challenges: uncertainty regarding the condition of returned appliances due to limited consumer data sharing, insufficient durability and longevity data from laboratory tests of new models, and operational inefficiencies due to inexperience with dismantling and refurbishing processes. To address these challenges, we propose advanced digital solutions leveraging Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), and Augmented Reality (AR) technologies. Specifically, IoT and AI-based systems are recommended for comprehensive product tracking, real-time condition monitoring, predictive maintenance, and informed decision-making, significantly improving data availability and accuracy for refurbishment operations. Additionally, we suggest AR-enhanced workstations to assist workers in dismantling processes, enhancing operational efficiency, reducing error rates, and facilitating knowledge management across diverse product models. Our findings extend the current body of knowledge on CE barriers, particularly in relation to IoT capabilities and consumer data-sharing practices and highlight practical implications for manufacturers seeking effective digital interventions. This research underscores the critical role of technology integration and organisational readiness in achieving successful CMS transitions.

Keywords: Circular Manufacturing Systems (CMS), Circular Economy (CE), Digital Transformation

Paper type: Academic Research Paper

1 Introduction

The circular economy (CE) is being considered a transformative business and sustainability paradigm, grounded in recognising that natural resources are finite and that traditional linear production models are unsustainable (Geissdoerfer *et al.*, 2017; Jensen, 2023). Central to this paradigm, as outlined by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation (EMF, n.d.), are the principles of (i) eliminating waste and pollution, (ii) keeping products and materials in use at their highest value, and (iii) regenerating natural systems. These principles recognise the constraints of finite natural resources and degrading environmental conditions as major drivers for companies to become circular and sustainable. These CE principles are adopted by implementing different CE practices, which are increasingly enabled using digital technologies (Neri *et al.*, 2023). The adoption of CE principles is even more important for the manufacturing sector to counter waste generation and increase the usability of products during their life cycle.

In manufacturing, the CE principles drive the development of Circular Manufacturing Systems (CMS), *designed intentionally for closing the loop of components or products, preferably in their original form, through multiple life cycles* (Rashid *et al.*, 2020, p. 345). The transition from linear to circular manufacturing is a complex, long-term initiative that linear companies usually undergo iteratively, focusing on three CMS pillars: product design, business model, and supply chains, which are enabled through ICT implementation and digital transformation. Companies usually pursue CMS through circular economy (CE) practices (Neri *et al.*, 2023). Despite the potential benefits of implementing CE, its adoption in linear manufacturing firms is still considered low. For example, the circular material use rate in the EU for 2023 was only 11.8% (EEA, 2025), indicating that the economy is primarily linear. To understand the reasons behind the slow adoption of CE, we explored the challenges that linear manufacturing companies face due to their current business model design, product design,

supply chain design, and existing ICT infrastructure. The research also explored the potential solutions to these challenges and the required knowledge and competencies.

To explore the challenges, we conducted an in-depth single case study of a European white goods manufacturer actively pursuing a transition towards CMS by establishing a dedicated return and refurbishment centre. This case was chosen because it reflects incumbent manufacturers' typical challenges when integrating CE practices into existing operations. Data were gathered for one year through a multi-method qualitative approach, including expert interviews, group interviews, focus groups and validation sessions. Subsequently, thematic analysis identified three challenges, and the participative design research approach generated potential ICT-based solutions.

This paper follows a standard structure, with theoretical background outlining the main theoretical concepts of this research, namely CMS, circular product design, circular business models, circular supply chains and digital support for CMS. Our qualitative methodology is described in the following chapter, focusing on data collection, thematic analysis, and a participatory design research approach. The identified challenges and the designed ICT-based solution are described in the results section. We contextualised our findings with respect to recent scientific developments in the discussion.

2 Theoretical background

The concept of CMS has finished the evolution of linear manufacturing from reverse approaches through closed-loop concepts, fuelled by the context of sustainability movements. The product design phase determines around 80% of the environmental impacts (European Commission, 2012) and is crucial for circularity as it determines the future reusability of the product. The most significant barriers hindering the transition towards circular product design are: financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, government inaction, and global market barriers (Wang et al., 2022). If these barriers could be overcome, the design should focus on preserving product integrity, developing a longitudinal value proposition, and having a longitudinal business model (den Hollander, 2018). Including reducing, reusing, recovering, and rethinking principles into the product design phase (Tan et al., 2024) can dramatically reduce the environmental impact. These CE practices or principles could pave the way towards CMS (Neri et al., 2023). However, isolated implementation of CE practices or focus only on product design does not ensure transformation to CMS. The typical manufacturing pillars (product design, business model, supply chains, ICT) should be integrated and developed together (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: CMS framework (Rashid et al., 2020, p. 346)

The business model needs to evolve together with circular product design into a circular business model that could be understood as a business model that is cycling, extending, intensifying, and/or dematerialising material and energy loops to reduce the resource inputs into and the waste and emission leakage out of an organisational system. This comprises recycling measures (cycling), use phase extensions (extending), a more intense use phase (intensifying), and the substitution of products by service and software solutions (dematerialising) (Geissdoerfer et al., 2020). Frishammar and Parida (2019) proposed a road map for circular business model transformation for linear companies, consisting from four phases i) analysing opportunities to initiate circular business model transformation; ii) review of current business model to identify gaps; iii) design and develop a revised business model based on the design elements of circular economy, iv) validate, implement and scale-up the circular

business model. Further integration of circular product design and business models with supply chain capabilities is needed.

The notion of circularity in supply chains emerged long before circularity became the central theme. Reverse logistics (Rogers and Tibben-Lembke, 2001; Tibben-Lembke and Rogers, 2002), or closed-loop supply chains (Guide and Van Wassenhove, 2006) have been studied for more than 20 years. However, these different concepts converged into circular supply chains (Wang *et al.*, 2022). The prevalence of linear manufacturing business models and thinking implies many barriers to successful circular supply chain implementation. For example, Taddei *et al.* (2024) identified seventeen barriers associated with circular supply chains. The authors ordered the barriers based on their importance, resulting in financial and economic barriers being the most important, followed by technical, legislative, political, organisational, and social barriers. In the recent study, Chen *et al.* (2025) identified factors affecting the implementation of circular supply chains. The immediate determinants were lower consumer costs, recycled raw material production, and energy conservation technology.

Technologies (mainly Industry 4.0) support all three pillars of CMS, as they play a significant role in the circularity transformation of supply chains, serving as enablers (Taddei *et al.*, 2024). Digital technologies were proven to support the circular economy strategies, especially in the areas of improving energy and resource efficiency, recycling, rethinking and reusing (Liu *et al.*, 2022). However, the same study highlighted that the repurpose strategy is the least supported by digital technologies. Digital technologies play a role of lower-order capability when supporting business performance through CE practices (Riggs *et al.*, 2024). This confirms the importance of digital technologies in CE initiatives, showing that digital technologies are a necessary but not sufficient condition for a successful CE initiative.

Some authors extended the focus on the four pillars (business model, product design, supply chain, ICT) by further areas. For example, Chirumalla *et al.* (2024) proposed a multi-level readiness framework to support the transition of manufacturing companies from linear to circular economy. They identified four key focus areas, each with five levels of progression: i) the ecosystem of external partners, ii) the customer and the business model, iii) the company's culture and internal capabilities, and iv) design and product development. The authors also identified four strategies for the successful transition to a circular economy: i) changing the mindset, ii) understanding of the circular economy concept and establishing own definition, iii) high-level planning and evaluation of scenarios, and iv) ensuring financial viability and environmental preservation.

3 Methodology

The goal of this research was to explore and describe the challenges of a manufacturing company aiming to transition from linear to circular manufacturing. The main research question this study addresses is: "What are the challenges that companies face when transitioning towards CMS, and how can digitalisation help address those challenges?" To answer this research question, we employed an exploratory, in-depth case study approach with features from design and action research strategies. The exploratory nature was derived from the lack of previous research that did not bring suitable testable outcomes. We chose the inductive qualitative approach because we wanted to provide details that could guide future confirmatory research. The design and action research elements were needed to answer the second part of the research question, as Company A could use the analysis of the barriers and our experience to design the solutions.

At the start of our research, we conducted several online interviews with relevant people from the organization. These interviews allowed us to understand the context of the company and its CMS transition initiatives. These interviews were recorded, and the transcripts were validated with the interviewees. After initial thematic analysis of the interviews, we designed a multiple-day focus group at the Company A facility to gather further data about the initial themes and ensure that we did not miss any themes during the initial interviews. The sample for the focus group was wider than the initial interviews, as we identified new respondents. The focus group was not recorded. However, multiple researchers were present during the focus group, and we created detailed notes that were validated after each session. The notes were used for further thematic analysis, both for conceptualising the existing themes further and identifying new themes. The themes were subsequently validated with relevant stakeholders through online interviews after the focus group.

After we concluded the thematic analysis, we designed another focus group that focused on exploring the design of digital solutions for overcoming the challenges. This focus group was conducted online using collaboration and co-creation tools both during and after the meeting to discuss and elaborate on different digital solutions. After the focus group, the authors prepared the circular flow diagram and mapped the digital solutions to different phases/stages of the circular value chain of the company (i.e., value use phase, reverse

logistics, and value recovery phase). Finally, the authors collected written feedback from the relevant people at the company on the need for different digital solutions and their design.

4 Findings

Company A operates in the white goods industry and manufactures a wide range of products that include refrigerators, freezers, washing machines, dishwashers, ovens, etc. For this research, only the business unit focusing on laundry appliances is considered, for which Company A is aiming to establish a refurbishment centre.

4.1 Current CMS maturity

Company A focused on CE activities and environmental awareness in the past decades by implementing an ISO-14001 environmental management system in 2000 and the EU Eco-Management and Audit Scheme (EMAS) in 2004. These activities helped reduce environmental impact in all the product life-cycle phases. Company A focuses on the long-term duration of appliances that support multiple lifecycles. The company tested a pay-per-use business model. Company A seeks to increase its value recovery activities by establishing and integrating refurbishment operations into its current processes. For this, Company A builds data infrastructure and data gathering capabilities through smart home features in their appliances, which are supported by IoT hardware to generate and gather data about the appliances.

To continue the transition to CMS, Company A wants to establish a refurbishment centre to refurbish appliances and harvest spare parts. Company A would like to use increased value recovery in the form of refurbished used parts to support their pay-per-use business model, to prepare to fulfil the future legislation about the right-to-repair, and to lower their costs on spare parts manufacturing. Therefore, Company A must ensure a sufficient volume of refurbished components and appliances, but it faces several challenges. The digital support for circularity remains limited. Company A also lacks the IT infrastructure to support the recovery and quality assessment of the used parts.

4.2 Challenges

During our thematic analysis, the following themes in the form of challenges emerged, which stand in the way towards CMS transformation:

- CHAL1 Uncertain condition of the appliance and its components
- CHAL2 Limited data about the longevity of the appliances for new models
- CHAL3 No experience with the dismantling process

The refurbishment centre will handle both unused and used appliances that have been returned. The first group will be easier to handle from the context of their condition. However, handling the used products will be challenging due to their uncertain condition (CHAL1). If the appliance has smart features, it could be connected, and Company A could have information (although usually impartial) about the use of the product. The real challenge will occur when there is no data about the use of the appliance online. The appliance stores a limited amount of data that could be retrieved and used for condition assessment; however, without further data that could be used to correlate the data from the appliance, it will be impossible to assess the appliance's condition.

Company A tests all models in a durability lab to check the average lifetime. The basic models take about eight months (non-stop usage) to test, whereas thoroughly testing the premium and heavy-duty models for their designed lifetime would take around seven years. This has two implications. First, some models cannot be adequately tested before entering the market. Second, Company A misses the data from testing for use in assessing the returned appliances. The extended testing time of the new models and limited data availability from their testing (although in laboratory conditions) make the efficiency of the refurbishment centre processes hard (CHAL2).

When establishing the new refurbishment initiative, the biggest challenge is the inexperience with the dismantling process and linear focus. The intake of many returned models contradicts the experience from linear manufacturing and complicates any (semi-) automation. Manual processes are prevalent and significantly depend on the expertise and knowledge of the inspection and dismantling workers. However, Company A has no extensive experience with these operations, and the lack of experience will result in errors and low efficiency of the inspection and dismantling processes (CHAL3).

4.3 Digital Solutions

We identified and designed two solutions (SOL) that are aimed at addressing the identified challenges. The first solution (SOL1) aims to enhance the IoT capability for tracing, tracking, and condition monitoring of washing

machines. It directly tackles CHAL1 and CHAL2 through Artificial Intelligence (AI) based decision support solutions with the aim to decrease testing time for new models of washing machines, increase uptime of washing machines during use phase, optimize reverse logistics of used appliances and parts, speed up end-of-life testing of used parts, and improve spare parts availability and inventory management. Table 1 provides a summary of IoT and AI-based digital solutions and their key requirements

Table 1: IoT & AI based circular support solutions and their key requirements

Area	Digital Solution	Key Requirements
Tracking & Tracing	Use of digital platform for collecting and storing operational data	a) 5 main data groups: settings, status, static, program status b) Cloud-based storage for long-term availability c) Requires enhanced firmware and software upgrades for cloud communication
Condition Monitoring of Critical Components	IoT-driven tracking of pump, heater, and motor performance	a) Monitoring of usage cycles, power consumption, and error codes b) Store data in a centralized data lake c) Data used for ML model training and maintenance forecasting
Durability Testing	Use of sensors for monitoring during lab testing	a) Custom firmware to read temperature and pressure sensors b) Streaming of raw sensor data (e.g., water temperature, pressure) c) IoT stack upgrade for low-latency, high-throughput data streaming
Reverse Logistics Decision Support	AI models to assess reuse and recovery decisions	a) Use of lifecycle data, error codes, and service logs b) ML pipeline using Apache Kafka and the Azure platform c) Support for end-of-life decision making (refurbish, recycle, buyback)
Predictive Maintenance	Machine learning for predicting component failures	a) Labeled training datasets from field failures b) Addressing the imbalance in data (rare failures) c) Use of supervised learning or anomaly detection d) Integration with historical error logs and operational patterns
AI Support for Durability Testing	Application of ML on lab testing data	a) Use of extended sensor logs b) Combination with historical technical data and component details c) Focus on improving label quality for model training
End-of-Life Testing	Data-based decision support for reuse or disassembly	a) ML models trained with sensor and statistical data b) Use of appliance and component-level information c) Labels such as “buyback” or “refurbish/recycle” guide decisions

The second solution (SOL2) should overcome CHAL3. To dismantle the appliances and recover the critical parts at the refurbishment centre, Company A will implement an AR-based solution to achieve a low error rate in value recovery of returned appliances. The proposed solution involves using an AR application in combination with a specific dismantling station to provide instructions for dismantling in a user-friendly manner.

Table 2: AR & AI-based digital solutions for disassembly and parts recovery

Area	Digital Solution	Key Requirements
Disassembly Support	AR-guided workstation for manual disassembly tasks	a) Physical station with camera setup and object tracking b) Adaptive instruction interface with text, images, videos, and 3D objects c) Latency under 40 ms for real-time response d) Validation of user interactions through object detection e) Offline mode capability f) Integration with Gorenje’s IT infrastructure and reverse logistics workflows

5 Conclusion

This study explored the challenges faced by manufacturing firms transitioning from linear to Circular Manufacturing Systems (CMS) and how digital technologies can address these challenges. Our research identified three key challenges: uncertain appliance condition due to limited user data sharing (CHAL1), inadequate product longevity data from laboratory tests (CHAL2), and operational inefficiencies arising from a lack of dismantling experience (CHAL3). We proposed advanced digital solutions, including IoT and AI for product tracking, condition monitoring, predictive maintenance, and decision support (SOL1), as well as augmented reality (AR) systems to assist manual disassembly processes (SOL2). These findings contribute to existing literature by expanding on identified barriers related to data complexity and IoT capability deficits (Ozkan-Ozen *et al.*, 2020). Specifically, we extended knowledge concerning user data-sharing barriers from supply chains into the white goods industry context. Additionally, our insights into operational inefficiencies due to workforce inexperience (see, Taddei *et al.*, 2024) align with social barriers identified in other sectors (Kazancoglu *et al.*, 2020), thereby broadening their applicability and relevance.

From a practical perspective, our study provides manufacturing firms with actionable insights into how digital transformation can facilitate the adoption of CMS. The integration of AI/ML and AR-assisted workstations represents a promising pathway to overcome existing challenges in data availability and operational inefficiencies. Such ICT-driven solutions improve the effectiveness of refurbishment processes and support the broader transition from linear to circular manufacturing models. For practitioners, the case study offers a replicable blueprint for designing and implementing refurbishment initiatives that are both technologically advanced and aligned with CE principles. This study contributes to the literature on digital transformation and circular manufacturing by exploring the challenges and opportunities associated with integrating ICT solutions in traditional manufacturing settings.

Our study provides actionable insights for practitioners aiming to transition toward circular manufacturing. Companies should invest in IoT technologies integrated with AI for real-time condition monitoring and predictive maintenance to improve decision-making in refurbishment operations. Manufacturing firms need to prioritise user-friendly IoT solutions to encourage consumer data sharing, addressing privacy concerns through transparent data management policies. Adoption of AR-guided workstations is recommended to enhance efficiency and accuracy in product disassembly and inspection processes.

Our findings underscore the importance of considering technological capabilities and organisational readiness when designing digital interventions. They also highlight the need for further confirmatory studies across diverse industrial sectors to assess the generalizability of the proposed solutions. Future research could extend our approach by incorporating multiple case studies, providing a more comprehensive understanding of how digital technologies can be leveraged to enhance CMS. Additionally, there is scope for investigating the socio-technical dimensions of digital transformation, particularly concerning workforce training and the user acceptance of smart technologies.

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7 Ethics declaration

The data collection in this paper did not have to be subject to ethical clearance; standard GDPR procedure was followed.

8 AI declarations

We used AI, namely Chatgpt Plus from Openai, to help with the quality of text. After the full draft of the paper was finished, we asked Chatgpt for critical feedback on our writing and used some of the suggestions for rewriting and improving the text.

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